

Extraction of lipid from cyanobacteria by different disruption methods : A comparative study

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Abstract : Production of biodiesel from different floral sources involves extraction of lipid followed by converting these into fatty acid methyl esters (FAME). Microalgae, the most popular third generation biofuel resource of the day, contain cell wall. Therefore, cell lysis process may also play an important role for extraction efficacy of lipid. In the present study three cyanobacterial strains were collected from East Kolkata Wetland, a Ramsar site of International Importance, and identified as *Anabaena anomala*, *Oscillatoria subbrevis*, and mixed consortium of *Oscillatoria subbrevis*, and *Gleocapsa atrata*, respectively. They were cultivated autotrophically in basal media, and the lipid content of these strains was determined individually. Different cell disruption techniques such as autoclaving, sonication, mortar pestle, and osmotic shock were adopted to lyse the cells. The extracted lipid was transesterified to FAME and the fatty acid composition was analysed using gas chromatography. The efficacy of different cell disruption techniques was compared by studying both the amount of extracted lipid, and fatty acid composition with that obtained from the respective undisrupted cells. Comparative analysis revealed that *Oscillatoria subbrevis* produced maximum lipid content of about 35.4% based on wet biomass by mortar pestle disruption technique. It was found that lipid content differed with the strains as well as with cell disruption methods.

Keywords : Lipid, biodiesel, FAME analysis, cell disruption technique, *Anabaena anomala*, *Oscillatoria subbrevis*, *Gleocapsa atrata*.

Introduction

Rapid increase in environmental pollution and depletion of fossil fuel are global threat. Thus, it is the need of the hour to develop renewable, environment friendly and sustainable form of energy. Fossil fuel provides 85% of the energy needed worldwide, and replacing it is a challenging task. Moreover, the resources developed should support sustainable development, and lower greenhouse gas emission¹. Biomass, especially biofuel has become a major contribution to international renewable energy needs. To overcome the limitations associated with first two generations of biofuels like scarcity of land area, water short-

age, and lesser biomass yield; third generation biofuels derived from microalgae has been developed which offers greater opportunity for further improvement². Microalgae are the potential feedstock for different types of renewable fuels such as biodiesel, methane, hydrogen, ethanol, etc.³. Biodiesel has a great potential to supplement conventional diesel fuel. Therefore, production of biodiesel from algal biomass can be a promising substitute of diesel produced from petroleum.

Microalgae have oil productivity greater than most oil producing crops⁴. Most of the work on biodiesel production by microalgae has been carried out using green al-

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gae, but there is another group of prokaryotic microalgae viz. cyanobacteria whose oil productivity matches with that of green microalgae. Cyanobacteria have a potential of producing 157.4–629.8 metric tons/annum of biomass with oil content of 20–40%⁴. Lipid content as high as 45% for *Cyanobacterium aponium*, 42.8% for *Synechococcus* sp. and 38.2% for *Phormidium* sp., have been reported by Karatay and Donmez⁵. Similar work has been carried out by Wahren and his team⁶ where the biodiesel production by both green algae and cyanobacteria has been compared. These studies suggest that cyanobacteria can be used as a potential feedstock for biodiesel production.

In the present study, three cyanobacterial strains were collected from East Kolkata Wetland region, India. This wetland system is popularly known as the ‘kidney of the city’ and is included in the list maintained under Ramsar Bureau established under the article 8 of the Ramsar Convention in 2002. It has a rich biodiversity that has given this wetland the recognition of a ‘Wetland of International importance’^{7,8}.

The conventional method to produce biodiesel comprises of three basic steps; cell disruption, followed by lipid extraction by solvent and finally transesterification of extracted lipid with alcohol in presence of suitable catalyst. Different studies have been conducted by varying the solvent used and extraction procedure⁹. In some studies the catalyst and alcohols used for transesterification reaction have also been varied to demonstrate their effect on lipid content and composition⁶. The cell disruption step plays a vital role as it depends on the characteristics of the microorganism under study. Little work has been carried out on different cell disruption techniques especially with cyanobacteria¹⁰. As cyanobacteria contain cell wall, the amount of extracted lipid may depend on efficacy of cell disruption. The present study focuses on the effect of different cell disruption methods on lipid content and composition of three cyanobacterial strains.

Results and discussion

Study of growth of the cyanobacterial strains : Three cyanobacterial strains were collected from three different points at East Kolkata Wetland, India and morphologically identified at Botanical Survey of India, Howrah as

Anabaena anotnala, *Oscillatoria subbrevis*, and mixed consortium of *Oscillatoria subbrevis* and *Gleocapsa atrata* respectively. The growth of cyanobacteria in basal synthetic media was determined in terms of dry biomass, and lipid contents on day to day basis as shown in Fig. 1a and Fig. 1b respectively.

From Fig. 1a it is seen that lag phase persisted up to 4 days after which log phase started. After 16 days of culture, stationary phase initiated. The declining nature of growth curve for strain of *Anabaena anomala* after 20 days may be due to the initiation of death phase. Dry biomass for *Anabaena anomala*, *Oscillatoria subbrevis* and mixed consortium of *Oscillatoria subbrevis* and *Gleocapsa atrata* had increased from 0.067, 0.031, 0.0765 g/L to 0.564, 0.172, 0.291 g/L, respectively during exponential phase. From Fig. 1b it is evident that lipid content of mixed algal consortium i.e. of *Oscillatoria subbrevis* and *Gleocapsa atrata* is much higher than that of unialgal strain of *Anabaena anomala* and *Oscillatoria subbrevis*. Maximum lipid obtained from *Anabaena anomala*, *Oscillatoria subbrevis* and mixed algal consortium of *Oscillatoria subbrevis* and *Gleocapsa atrata*, were 7.36, 6.5 and 11.5% respectively.

In Table 1 the biomass productivity (P_B) and lipid yield (P_L) of each sample had been represented. The biomass productivity of *Anabaena anomala* was highest followed by mix culture of *Oscillatoria subbrevis* and *Gleocapsa atrata*, while least biomass was obtained from *Oscillatoria subbrevis*. It is known that *Anabaena* sp., being the nitrogen fixing strain is responsible for algal bloom and eutrophication of water bodies, so it has little lipid production capability while because of high assimilation ability of both CO₂ and N₂, it produces high biomass. Therefore, the biomass productivity of *Anabaena* sp. was highest but lipid yield was lowest.

Table 1. Biomass productivity and lipid yield of different strains

	Lag phase (days)	Stationary phase (days)	Biomass productivity (mg/L/d)	Lipid yield (mg/mg/L/d)
<i>A. anomala</i>	4	18	28.73	4.47
<i>O. subbrevis</i>	4	16	9.58	5.28
Mixed culture of <i>O. subbrevis</i> and <i>G. atrata</i>	4	16	18.96	13.86

Fig. 1a. Growth curve of three cyanobacterial strains.

Fig. 1b. Variation of lipid content of three cyanobacterial strains with time. Sample A : *Anabaena anomala*, Sample B : *Oscillatoria subbrevis*, Sample C : *Oscillatoria subbrevis* and *Gleocapsa atrata*.

Lipid extracted by different lysis processes : The amount of total lipid extracted using different lysis processes, both from wet and dry biomass for each strain is shown in Fig. 2. In control, lipid was extracted from cells without any disruption method. Maximum lipid (35.4%) was

found from *Oscillatoria subbrevis* wet biomass by mortar and pestle method while minimum lipid (4.4%) was obtained from mixed culture of *Oscillatoria subbrevis* and *Gleocapsa atrata* when lysed by sonication using dry biomass.

In case of wet biomass, *Oscillatoria subbrevis* provides best result with mortar and pestle method followed by *Anabaena anomala* with autoclave method, mixed culture of *Oscillatoria subbrevis* and *Gleocapsa atrata* with mortar and pestle method and *Oscillatoria subbrevis* treated with osmotic shock. On the contrary, for dry biomass, sonication of strain *Oscillatoria subbrevis* gave best result, followed by strain *Anabaena anomala* with autoclave method and mortar and pestle method respectively (Fig. 2).

Grinding the cells mechanically by applying pressure is a simple and effective method of cell disruption. Grinding of wet biomass was easier and more efficacious than grinding already dried cells. All the dry samples gave similar yield of lipid (15.47 to 16.05%) while with wet biomass *Oscillatoria subbrevis* and mixed culture of *Oscillatoria subbrevis* and *Gleocapsa atrata* gave much higher yield (35.4% and 24.67% respectively).

When high frequency waves of 10 KHz were applied for disrupting the cells, it was found to be more effective in wet biomass as cell membranes are more intact in freshly harvested cells than already dried cells. *Oscillatoria subbrevis*, however, showed a different trend where dry biomass gave 21.93% lipid yield.

Disruption of the cells at high temperature and pressure produced a huge difference in the lipid quantity of all the strains in both wet and dry condition. Lipid content of 28.91% was obtained with wet biomass of *Anabaena anomala* while about 21.04% with its already dried biomass. Similar trend with mixed culture of *Oscillatoria subbrevis* and *Gleocapsa atrata* has been observed with wet biomass (16.9%) and dry biomass (8.5%). *Oscillatoria subbrevis* again shows a different pattern in lipid content obtained (Fig. 2).

However, *Oscillatoria subbrevis* under osmotic shock provided both highest (23.21% with wet sample) and lowest (8.31% with dry sample) lipid yield. Mixed culture of *Oscillatoria subbrevis* and *Gleocapsa atrata* showed analogous result. For *Anabaena anomala* dry version produced better yield.

Amount of extracted lipid differed with respect to strains and cell disruption methods. *Anabaena anomala*, with wet biomass produced maximum lipid (28.91%) by autoclaving and with dry biomass produced minimum lipid (8.1%) through sonication, while mortar and pestle method produced similar result in both wet (14.74%) and dry (16.05%) condition.

Fig. 2. Lipid content (%) of different samples using different cell disruption methods. Sample A : *Anabaena anomala*, Sample B : *Oscillatoria subbrevis*, Sample C : *Oscillatoria subbrevis* and *Gleocapsa atrata*.

For *Oscillatoria subbrevis* mortar and pestle method produced the maximum lipid (35.4%) with wet biomass and with dry biomass minimum lipid (8.31%) was obtained through osmotic shock treatment. For *Oscillatoria subbrevis* and *Gleocapsa atrata*, sonication produced the minimum lipid (4.45%) while mortar and pestle method produced the maximum yield (24.67%).

In our study it was found, of all strains *Oscillatoria subbrevis* was proved to be the most promising feedstock. Mortar and pestle was the most effective cell disruption technique for biodiesel production. Similar findings have been reported by Lee *et al.*¹¹ where mechanical treatment like bead beating has extracted higher lipid content from green algae than sonication, homogenization, French press or lyophilisation.

Analysis of fatty acid methyl esters : The FAME composition of all the cyanobacteria has been determined by gas chromatography. Mortar and pestle method showed the maximum lipid yield in *Oscillatoria subbrevis* while sonication displayed lowest lipid yield, therefore gas chromatography analysis of all the strains on these two methods is listed in Table 2. Palmitic acid (C16 : 0) was found to be most abundant in all the strains of the cell disruption

methods used. Its amount was maximum (36%) with mortar and pestle in *Anabaena anomala*. In general it is said that oil with high oleic acid content have been reported to have a reasonable balance of fuel properties¹⁰. The highest oleic acid content was obtained in mixed culture of *Oscillatoria subbrevis* and *Gleocapsa atrata* (22%) in both the methods. Its amount was about 45.77% with mortar pestle method in *Anabaena anomala*.

It has been found that not only the lipid yield but also the FAME composition varied with cell disruption procedure. Most of the fatty acids in biological system do not remain in free form but in esterified form. For biodiesel triacyl glycerol is considered as the chief source of fatty acid. Apart from that fatty acid may be obtained from wax ester, steryl esters, glycolipids and phospholipids of cell membrane. Relative abundance of fatty acids in above lipid classes is also different. When different cell disruption methods were employed, the above mentioned lipid classes might not have been extracted uniformly resulting difference in FAME composition.

Earlier it had been reported¹² that fatty acid and FAME with four or more double bonds are susceptible to oxidation during storage and this reduces their acceptability

Table 2. Fatty acid methyl esters composition of different strains by different methods of cell disruption (Mortar and pestle method and Sonication)

FAME content (%)	<i>Anabaena anomala</i>			<i>Oscillatoria subbrevis</i>			Mix culture of <i>O. subbrevis</i> and <i>G. atrata</i>		
	Control	Mortar and pestle	Sonication	Control	Mortar and pestle	Sonication	Control	Mortar and pestle	Sonication
Below C14 : 0	5.97	4.27	7.00	30.02	19.51	10.87	32.56	17.59	10.81
C14 : 0	3.44	7.27	2.34	14.14	1.35	1.26	11.39	2.11	1.20
C14 : 1	–	1.05	0.77	–	0.42	0.99	–	0.61	1.26
C16 : 0	47.14	37.84	29.4	25.35	31.15	33.22	22.66	28.77	32.01
16 : 1	4.63	10.15	16.54	4.33	11.36	12.77	4.18	9.29	11.19
C18 : 0	9.58	4.41	2.63	9.77	3.93	4.90	5.92	4.55	3.21
<i>cis</i> C18 : 1 n-9	17.44	2.74	12.97	–	12.89	1.70	–	22.10	26.92
<i>trans</i> C18 : 1 n-9	–	15.14	0.63	2.96	0.86	14.50	7.38	1.57	2.87
<i>cis</i> C18 : 2 n-6	6.25	10.26	3.27	2.98	12.00	12.13	2.06	5.61	6.48
<i>trans</i> C18 : 2 n-6	–	–	3.02	–	1.82	–	–	1.27	1.84
C18 : 3 n-6	–	–	18.58	–	2.27	–	1.34	–	1.72
C18 : 3 n-3	2.08	3.75	2.32	4.84	–	5.85	2.79	1.47	–
Above C18	3.28	3.03	–	4.85	1.97	0.81	6.66	4.46	–

Values represent relative amounts, expressed as percentage of total identified FAMES by weight.

Values shown are the average of three different analyses with deviation not exceeding 5% in each case.

for use as biodiesel specially for vehicle use. Such polyunsaturated fatty acids were absent in the cyanobacterial strains studied. It was found that FAME was mostly composed of chain length C-14 to C-18, making it prospective to be used as biodiesel.

Experimental

Chemicals and reagents : Solvents like chloroform, methanol, hexane, and other common chemicals were of AR grade and were purchased from Merck, India. Solvents were distilled before use.

Strains and culture : The three individual cyanobacterial strains were collected individually and cultivated in same BG-11 media. The composition of the BG-11 media per litre was NaNO₃ 1.5 g, K₂HPO₄ 0.04 g, MgSO₄·7H₂O 0.075 g, CaCl₂·2H₂O 0.036 g, citric acid 0.006 g, ferric ammonium citrate 0.006 g, EDTA 0.001 g, Na₂CO₃ 0.02 g and trace metal solution 1 mL. The components of trace metal solution per litre was H₃BO₃ 2.86 g, MnCl₂·4H₂O 1.81 g, ZnSO₄·7H₂O 0.222 g, NaMoO₄·5H₂O 0.390 g, CuSO₄·5H₂O 0.079 g, CO(NO₃)₂·6H₂O 0.0494 g. Volume of culture was maintained at 200 mL. All of these strains were incubated at 25 ± 2 °C in 500 ml Erlenmeyer flasks with continuous illumination by natural light during day and artificial source (2400 lux) after sunset which represents a Light : Dark cycle as 24 : 0. It was grown in the media for two weeks. The cells were then centrifuged and sub-cultured in fresh autoclaved media aseptically.

Cell harvesting and drying : The cultured cells were harvested by vacuum filtration, and the wet cell biomass was dried at 60 °C overnight in a hot air oven.

Cell disruption : Various methods like mortar and pestle, osmotic shock, autoclaving, and sonication were tested to identify the most effective one for cell disruption. A comparative study was conducted using wet and dry biomass of each cyanobacterial strain for lipid extraction. For extraction using wet biomass, the strains were filtered through vacuum filter, and tapped dry; whereas to get dry biomass, all the strains were dried at 60 °C in hot air oven overnight. The dry biomass was determined gravimetrically. Cyanobacterial cell biomass was prepared for extraction by mixing with 20 ml of distilled water, and the mixture was disrupted using four different methods such as (1) autoclaving at 125 °C for 5 min, (2) osmotic

shock using 10% NaCl solution, vortex for 1 min, and left for 48 h, (3) mechanically grinding using mortar pestle, and (4) sonication using bath sonicator (Microson Ultrasonic Cell Disruptor) at a resonance of 10 KHz for 5 min.

Lipid extraction : The total lipid was extracted using Bligh and Dyer method¹³ using a solvent mixture of chloroform and methanol in the ratio of 2 : 1 (v/v). After cell disruption 20 ml solvent was added to the mixture, and it was vortex for 10 min. The mixture was transferred into a separating funnel and shaken for 5 min. After separation, the lower organic phase was collected in capped tubes and the solvent was evaporated using a rotary evaporator under reduced pressure. The weight of the lipid was determined gravimetrically. Lipid extracted by the same procedure without using any cell disruption method was treated as control.

The lipid content was calculated as

$$L_C = \frac{W_{L,t}}{W_{B,t}} \times 100$$

where, $W_{L,t}$ = weight of lipid obtained at day t, and $W_{B,t}$ = weight of biomass obtained at day t.

The biomass productivity was calculated by the following equation

$$P_B = \frac{(W_B - W_{B0}) \times 1000}{V \times t}$$

where, W_B = weight of dry biomass obtained at the onset of stationary phase (mg), W_{B0} = weight of dry biomass in inoculums (mg), V = volume of culture (ml), t = days for attaining stationary phase.

The lipid yield (P_L) was calculated as follows :

$$P_L = \frac{W_L}{P_B}$$

where, W_L = amount of lipid extracted from biomass obtained at the onset of stationary phase (mg).

Transesterification of fatty acid : The extracted lipid was transesterified into fatty acid methyl ester (FAME) using 1% sulphuric acid in methanol. It was mixed well and refluxed for 2 h, extracted with hexane, and purged with nitrogen gas to prevent further oxidation.

FAME analysis : FAMES were purified by thin layer chromatography, and analysed by gas chromatograph (Agilent 7820A) with FID using DB 23 column (30 m, 0.25 mm, 0.25 μ m). Nitrogen gas was used as carrier with a flow rate of 1.927 ml/min. The injector and detector temperature were 250 °C and 300 °C respectively. The initial oven temperature was 50 °C for 1 min, then it was raised up to 175 °C at the rate of 25 °C/min and up to 230 °C at the rate of 4°C/min and held there for 5 min. FAMES were identified by comparing their retention times with those of the standards (Supelco 37 component mixture) while the area under the peaks determined their quantity.

Results were expressed as Mean \pm SD.

Conclusions

In the present study, Cyanobacteria were collected from different places of East Kolkata Wetland, West Bengal. The samples collected were *Anabaena anomala*, *Oscillatoria subbrevis*, and mixed culture of *Oscillatoria subbrevis* and *Gleocapsa atrata*.

Oscillatoria subbrevis and *Gleocapsa atrata* has shown biomass productivity of 18.96 mg/L/d. maximum lipid content of 11.5% and it had a lag phase of about 4 days, while it reached stationary phase in 16 days. *Anabaena anomala* and *Oscillatoria subbrevis* have shown lipid content of 0.5% and 7.4%, respectively.

It can be concluded that efficiency of lipid extraction from cyanobacteria differ according to the species under study and extraction method used. The highest lipid yield was obtained from *Oscillatoria subbrevis* (35.4%) with wet biomass and mortar and pestle disruption technique while minimum lipid (4.4%) was obtained from *Oscillatoria subbrevis* and *Gleocapsa atrata* when disrupted by sonication using dry biomass. However, sonication has given better result with *Oscillatoria subbrevis* (21%). Autoclaving *Anabaena anomala* at a high temperature, and pressure, produced 21% of the total lipid.

Thus it can be stated that out of the four methods performed, mortar and pestle was the most simple, easy, and effective cell disruption technique, and *Oscillatoria subbrevis* of all the other strains was the most promising feedstock for biodiesel production.

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